

MALWARE DETECTION USING ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE TECHNIQUES

A

PROJECT PRESENTED

BY

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DECLARATION

I hereby declare that the project work entitled “ Malware Detection Using Artificial Intelligence Technique” is a collection of my original research work and it has not been presented for any other qualification anywhere. Information from other sources (published or unpublished) has been duly acknowledged.

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CERTIFICATION PAGE

This is to certify that this project work “Malware Detection Using Artificial Intelligence Technique” was carried out by Ebri Victor Iwara with Matric Number 17283102 meets the regulations governing the award of the degree of Bachelor of Science in Computer Science of the University of Abuja and it is approved for its contribution to scientific Knowledge and literary presentation.

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DEDICATION

This project work is dedicated to ALMIGHTY GOD who through his infinite mercy, love, grace, and kindness has been my source of inspiration till the end of this project work, and my wonderful and supporting friend, Ekundayo Idris.

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ABSTRACT

It is highly important to detect a file if there is any malware is present or not. Due to increase in malware, a lot of problems are created and companies are losing their important data and facing various problems. The next point is that malware can easily create a lot of damage to the system by slowing it down and also crypt many files in the personal computer. With rapid technological advancement, security has become a major issue due to the increase in malware activity that poses a serious threat to the security and safety of both computer systems and stakeholders. To maintain stakeholder's, particularly, end user's security, protecting the data from fraudulent efforts is one of the most pressing concerns. A set of malicious programming code, scripts, active content, or intrusive software that is designed to destroy intended computer systems and programs or mobile and web applications is referred to as malware. According to the study, naive users are unable to distinguish between malicious and benign applications. Thus, computer systems and mobile applications should be designed to detect malicious activities towards protecting the stakeholders. A number of algorithms are available to detect malware activities by utilizing novel concepts including Artificial Intelligence, Machine Learning, and Deep Learning. In this study, we emphasize Artificial Intelligence (AI) based techniques for detecting and preventing malware activity. We present a detailed review of current malware detection technologies, their shortcomings, and ways to improve efficiency. Our study shows that adopting futuristic approaches for the development of malware detection applications shall provide significant advantages. The comprehension of this synthesis shall help researchers for further research on malware detection and prevention using Artificial Intelligence.

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CHAPTER ONE

INTRODUCTION

1.1 BACKGROUND OF THE STUDY

The term malware is a malicious software that affects a host machine without the knowledge of its owner. It then carries out unauthorized activities, for example, damaging the host machine or stealing valuable data (Jang-Jaccard & Nepal 2014). Malware activities can be local to the host machine or propagated through the network to infect other machines as well. More than 500 million malware have been detected so far in 2016 (AVTest 2016). A staggering trend was observed in 2014 as 317 million malware were identified as new malware variants compared to 252 million malware in 2013, which is an increase of 26 percent (Symantec Corporation 2015). malware, like any other cyber threat, is any software intentionally designed to cause damage to a server, client, or computer network. Cyber attackers do the damage after which it is implanted or introduced in some way into a target's computer and can take the form of executable code, scripts, active content, or clone software. Threats like malware have been in existence for decades but they were referred to as computer viruses Hence, the term malware was introduced (Israel Rada 1990).

Many of these early infectious programs were actually written as pranks or experiments, but hackers now use malware to steal businesses, financial and personal information. A user or organization's critical data is encrypted so that they cannot access files, databases, or applications in their server. As a result, to such criminal activities, this malware was found to have some logistical problems on their method of receiving ransom which could be a risk to the developers because their identity could be discovered. Therefore, the developers decided to create a fake antivirus in order to prevent their identity from getting exposed.

Terms such as "worm", "virus", "Trojan horse" are used to classify malware samples that exhibit malicious behavior. The first instances of malicious software were viruses. There are several types of malicious software floating around the internet. Many of them have existed for years. With the advent of computers, malware arose from the dark side. programs known as rootkits were established and cyber attackers who hacked systems with criminal intent used this applications to hide their presence while they had their way with an unsuspecting organization's infrastructure.

(Rich Skrenta 1982) wrote a gem called "Elk Cloner" for apple two computers. The first known virus targeted at apple computer. At the time, it was probably the biggest target. As

malware defense matured, so did malware sophistication, other types of malicious programs emerged, including those that propagate without any help from the user population known as worms, they are probably today's biggest challenge to malware defense. Presently, the world is experiencing phenomenal advances in the computer field; however, the internationalization of cybercrime has also increased. In particular, during the COVID-19 pandemic, the heavy reliance on digital systems has led to a high increase of malware, such as ransomware. COVID-19 has played an essential role in the proliferation of cyber threats, while organizations and individuals struggle to adapt to unpredictable new norms, further arming cyber attackers with modernized tools and techniques to execute more dangerous cyberattacks. (Levi A.,2022).

The current landscape of cyberattacks has led to an era of cyberwarfare, with no limit or boundaries, and with very active cyber espionage (sometimes between states or even between sovereign bodies). One of the most effective defenses used in the context of cyberwarfare mainly focuses on the use of modern malware. With this level of adoption coupled with the open-source nature of Computer applications, security attacks are becoming more and more ubiquitous and seriously threaten the integrity of computer applications. Statistics shows that more than 50 million malware and potentially unwanted applications (PUA) have been identified for Computer system (Odusami et al 2018).

1.2 STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

As dangerous as malware is, you are not completely helpless against it. Malware has continued to grow at an exponential rate among computer systems, in spite the introduction and design of sophisticated anti-virus, and scanning techniques to detect and fight malware. Which brought about the rise to necessitate a control measure (artificial intelligence) that will assist the rate at which computer systems crash due to malware. Internet Security has become a major issue to deal with due to the increase in malware activity that poses a serious threat to the security and safety of both computer system and its users. Therefore, protecting the data from fraudulent efforts is one of the researcher's pressing concerns. Malware has continued to grow at an exponential rate among computer systems, in spite the introduction and design of sophisticated anti-virus, and scanning techniques, to detect and fight malware. Which brought rise, to the necessity to model a control measure that will assist the rate at which computer systems crash due to malware. Artificial Intelligence cannot automatically detect and resolve every potential malware or Cyber threat incident, but when it combines with the modeling of both bad and good behaviour, it can be successful and powerful weapon against even the most advanced malware.

1.3 AIMS AND OBJECTIVES

The purpose of this project is to emphasize how Machine Learning (AI) based techniques could be deployed to detect and prevent malware activity.

The objectives are:

- Perform an in-depth analysis of a specific dataset related to real malware traffic.
- Provide a taxonomy of potential Deep Learning techniques that may be used to enhance cybersecurity solution.
- Develop a new security approach based on a dynamic deep learning model for the autonomous detection and mitigation of modern (known and unknown) malware.

This will eventually show that adopting future approaches for the development of malware detection applications will provide significant advantages to combat malware to a very high degree. The comprehension of this aim and objective shall help researchers for further research on malware detection and prevention using Artificial Intelligence.

1.4 SIGNIFICANCE OF THE STUDY

The model approach is for individuals, public and co-operate organizations. Usage of this approach will help in detecting and reducing malware in our computer network. The need to detect malware and prevent it from damaging a system is very crucial. Malware can steal sensitive information from your computer, gradually slowing down your computer, or even send fake emails from your email account without you knowing and this may cause the device to crash and allow cybercriminals to steal or destroy your data. At the very least, it can create performance issues that hinder effective use of the device.

1.5 SCOPE AND LIMITATION OF THE STUDY

Due to limited resources, only 20 features are finally used in modeling. Although possibly the best 20 features are selected through feature selection methods, it is possible that a few important may have been missed.

The project is highly dependent on the datasets created by external researchers. The authenticity and robustness of the data are not verified. Consequently, we should be careful when generalizing the results of the project.

The project is limited to the two malware detection approaches, permissions-based and signatures-based. There could be other approaches that will give better performance than the ones considered in this project.

Adopting futuristic techniques for the development of robust security tools and antivirus is today's priority. This research covers the detection of malware variants created to destroy computer system and the detection tool the researcher is going to work with is Artificial Intelligence (AI), this will advance the fields of malware detection and prevention with the possibility to develop efficient, robust, and scalable malware recognition modules. The limitations that have been faced by the researcher are class imbalance, open and public benchmarks, concept drift, adversarial learning, and interpretability of models. the model limited to unforeseen circumstance, like malfunctioning of some of the computer parts, the lifespan of the computer and the durability.

1.6 RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

In this work, Malware detection approaches are divided into two main categories that include behavior-based and signature-based methods. Also, there are two static and dynamic malware analysis that generally performed in finding malicious applications. the researcher has illustrated a malware detection taxonomy based on machine learning approaches. In that, the Application Program Interface calls features, assembly features, and binary features are existing approaches for malware detection method. These features use Artificial Intelligence Techniques for predicting and detecting malicious files. The step-by-step methodology followed in this project is illustrated below.

- ***Chi-Square Test:***

This statistical test for categorical variables is conducted to check which of the features are more associated with the class variable. The top 20 of such highly associated features are selected.

Exploratory Analysis:

In this step, visualizations are used to deep dive into the data.

- The data is split into two classes – malware and benign.
- Each feature is explored individually, and I try to see the distribution of values of the feature when split by the class variable.
- This step helps in identifying the potentially differentiating features. The features whose distributions differ significantly between malware and benign classes will likely be the most important features.

Modeling using Supervised Classification Algorithms:

- The dataset is first broken up into training and testing datasets.
- The training set is used to train the classification algorithm, while the testing set is used to validate the results seen on the training set and address overfitting issues.

- Three different supervised classification algorithms are used for each approach to perform the classification into benign and malware classes.
- These algorithms are – K-nearest neighbors algorithm, Logistic Regression, and Random Forest.

Model Performance Measurement:

- Performance measurement of the classification process is first done using the confusion matrix.
- Additional performance measures are also calculated and used as the basis for comparison.
- **Precision:** measures how many of the applications the model classifies as malware are true malware – should be as high as possible
- **Recall:** measures how many of the malware samples in the dataset are correctly classified as malware – should be as high as possible
- **F1-score:** It is the harmonic mean between precision and recall and measures the overall accuracy of the model – it should be as high as possible.

Performance Comparison:

After all the models are built, results are compared to identify the best model and approach.

- A recall score is selected for comparison.
- In a malware detection problem, it is more important to identify all the true malware correctly than to ensure that all the malware identified is actually true malware. Therefore, recall is more important than precision.
- A comparison of recall scores is made first between the three classification algorithms within each approach. This helped in identifying the best algorithm for each approach.
- A comparison of recall scores is then made between the two approaches. This helped in identifying the best approach for the purpose of malware detection.

1.7 CHAPTER LAYOUT

It contains five chapters, Chapter one talks about the overall purpose of detecting malware using artificial intelligence.

Chapter two describes the importance of moving from classical malware detection and analysis to smart and autonomous detection/analysis through the incorporation of advanced

AI techniques. Moreover, we provide a classification of modern malware based on famous samples and high-profile cases.

Chapter three highlights the most common related work for malware detection and analysis.

Chapter four presents the proposed work and our methodology to deal with modern malware detection and mitigation. The experimental results are described also followed by some discussions.

Finally, Chapter five presents our conclusion and some future works.

1.8 DEFINITION OF TERMS

Anti-virus: designed to detect and destroy computer malware. (Wikipedia 2001)

Crash: occurs when a computer program, such as a software application or an operating system, stops functioning properly and exits.

Computer: is an electronic device that is capable of receiving information(data) in a particular form and performing a sequence of operations in accordance with a predetermined but variable set of procedural instructions (program) to produce a result in the form of information or signals.(Science Direct 2002).

Equilibrium stability: an equilibrium is said to be stable if the system always returns to its original state after being disturbed slightly.

Recovery: is an act or process of returning to a normal state of health, mind and strength.

Scanning: looks at all parts of something carefully in order to detect some feature.

Vulnerability: the ability or state of being exposed to the possibility of being attacked or harmed, either physically or emotionally.

CHAPTER TWO

LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 DETECTION OF MALWARE

Malware is a general term that encompasses viruses, Trojans, spyware and other invasive code that is widespread today. Malware analysis is a multi-step process providing insight into malware structure and functionality, facilitating the expansion of remedy.

The artificial Intelligence technique allows malware researchers to predict damage from a new threat Zou et al. (2002), understand the behavior of malware, including spreading characteristics Garetto et al. (2003), understand the factors affecting the malware spread, determine the required effectiveness of countermeasures in order to control the spread and facilitate network designs that are resilient to malware attacks Ramachandran and Sikdar(2004), predict the failures of the global network infrastructure Serazi and Zanero (2004).

2.1.0 BRIEF ABOUT ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE

Artificial intelligence (AI) is a technological phenomenon that all industries wish to exploit to benefit from efficiency gains and cost reductions because of its capability of replacing humans by undertaking intelligent tasks that were once limited to the human mind (Hassani et al., 2020).

(Nones et al., 2019) define AI as the rapidly growing development of computer systems that are able to perform tasks that only human intelligence could ever accomplish. However, from the aspects of scholars, AI can be used for intelligence augmentation (IA) instead of being a replacement for the human mind which gives it strategic importance with identifying as a potential key driver of the current technological revolution. Thus, AI can be widely used in developing projects based on intellectual processes including the capacity for augmentation, conception, consciousness, investigation, enthusiastic information, thinking, arranging, innovation, and problem-solving in different sectors including Big Data, Security, Business Analytics and many more domains (Ahn et al., 2019).

There are many types and ways AI can be achieved and machine learning is one of them which enables computers to imitate and adapt human-like behavior(Alizubi, 2018). Fig. 1 illustrates the types and uses of Artificial Intelligence consists of Machine Learning and Natural Language Processing. Machine learning (ML) can be defined field of study that encompasses automatic computing procedures to computers to attain AI without being

explicitly programmed based on logical or binary operations that learn a task from a series of examples (Ayodele, 2010). Such understanding and learning through circumstances techniques of machine learning, AI can be the stepping stone for the application to prevent computer viruses and malware.

2.1.1 ANTI-MALWARE AND SIGNATURE-BASED DETECTION

A traditional defense mechanism against malware attacks employed by anti-malware software is a signature-based detection and as such, an anti-malware software could for example scan files for known byte-sequence previously identified in a large signature repository. If the anti-malware finds matches of byte sequences, the software classifies the file as malware. Anti-malware repository is based on the identification of malware by researchers and analysts based on heuristic features. As a result, anti-malware has low false positive rates (wrongly classifying a benign file as malware) but fails to detect unknown malware. Furthermore, malware owners can easily bypass traditional anti-malware by obfuscation and inserting dummy or garbage code to modify the file's byte sequence (Sukwong et al. 2011).

2.2. TAXONOMY OF MALWARE

Malicious software, also known as malware, is any kind of software that is specifically designed to disrupt, damage, or gain unauthorized access to a computer system or network. Depending on the proliferation system, malware can be divided into various, not mutually exclusive categories.

- **Adware.** Malware designed to automatically generate online advertisements. This type of malware generates revenue for its developer by displaying advertisements on the user interface or the screen.
- **Backdoor.** Computer software that is designed to bypass a system's security mechanism and install itself on a computer to allow the attacker to access it.
- **Bot.** Software created to automatically perform specific operations such as DDoS attacks or distribute other malware. Bots are part of a botnet, a network of interconnected devices, which are controlled using command and control (C&C) software.
- **Downloader.** A downloader program's purpose is to download and install additional malicious programs.
- **Launcher.** A launcher is a computer program designed to stealthily launch other malicious programs.

- Ransomware. Malicious software that restricts user access to the computer system by encrypting the files or locking down the system while demanding a ransom for its release.
- Rootkit. Malware designed to conceal the existence of other malicious programs.
- Spyware. Computer software that spies and collects sensitive information without permission from a victim's computer. examples include key-loggers, password grabbers and sniffers.
- Trojan. A Trojan is a type of malicious software that disguises itself as legitimate software to trick users into downloading and installing malware on their systems.
- Virus. Malicious software that can propagate itself from device to device.
- Worm. A type of virus that exploits vulnerabilities of the operating system to spread. The major difference between worms and viruses is the ability of worms to independently self-replicate and spread while viruses depend on human activity.

Figure 2: Malware detection (Samantray et al., 2018)

2.3. MALWARE ANALYSIS

The process of dissecting malware to understand how it works, determine its functionality, origin and potential impact is called malware analysis. With millions of new malicious programs in the world, and the mutated versions of previously detected programs, total malware encountered by security analysts has been growing over the past years. Consequently, malware analysis is critical to any business and infrastructure that responds to security incidents.

There are two fundamental approaches to malware analysis: **static analysis** and **dynamic analysis**. On one hand, static analysis involves examining the malware without running it. On the other hand, dynamic analysis involves running the malware. An in-depth description of both approaches is provided in Sections 2.3.1 and 2.3.2.

2.3.1. STATIC ANALYSIS

The static analysis consists of examining the code or structure of the executable file without executing it. This kind of analysis can confirm whether a file is malicious. Information about its functionality can also be used to produce a simple set of signatures. For instance, the most common method used to uniquely identify a malicious program is hashing. That is, a hashing program produces a unique hash, a sort of fingerprint, that identifies the program. The two most popular hash functions are the Message-Digest Algorithm 5 (MD5) and the Secure Hash Algorithm 1 (SHA-1). The most common static analysis approaches are:

- Finding sequences of characters or strings. Searching through the strings of a program is the simplest way to obtain hints about its functionality. Strings extracted from the binary can contain references to filepaths of files modified or accessed by the URLs to which the program accesses domain names, IP addresses, attack commands, names of Windows dynamic link libraries (DLLs) loaded, registry keys, and so on..
- Gathering the linked libraries and functions of an executable, as well as the metadata about the file is included in the headers. These data provide information about code libraries and functionalities common to many programs, that programmers link so that they do not need to re-implement a certain functionality. The names of this Windows functions can give us an idea of what the executable does. The utility Dependency Walker is a free program for Microsoft Windows used to list the imported and exported functions of a PE file.
- Analyze PE file headers and sections. The PE file headers provide more information than just imports. They contain metadata about the file itself, such as the actual sections of the file. One way to retrieve this information is with the PE View tool.
- Searching for packed/encrypted code. Malware writers usually use packing and encryption to make their files more difficult to analyze. Software programs that have been packed or encrypted usually contain very few strings and higher entropy compared to legitimate programs. One way to detect packed files is with the PE id program

- Disassembling the program, that is, translating machine code into assembly language. This reverse-engineering process loads the executable into a disassembler to discover what the program does. The most relevant software programs for disassembling PE executables are IDA Pro, Radare2, and Ghidra.

2.3.2. DYNAMIC ANALYSIS

Dynamic analysis involves executing the program and monitoring its behavior on the system. This is typically performed when static analysis has reached a dead end, either due to obfuscation or on having exhausted the available static analysis techniques. Unlike static analysis, it traces the real actions executed by the program. However, the analysis must be run in a safe environment to not expose the system to unnecessary risks, where the system is both the machine running the analysis tool and the rest of the machines on the network. To this end, dedicated physical or virtual machines are set up.

Physical machines must be set up on air-gapped networks, that is isolated networks where machines are disconnected from the Internet or any other network, to prevent malware from spreading. The main downside of physical machines is this scenario with no Internet connection, as many malicious programs depend on an Internet connection for updates, command and control, and other features.

The second option is to set up virtual machines to perform dynamic analysis. A virtual machine emulates a computer system and provides the functionality of a physical computer. The OS running in the virtual machine is kept isolated from the host OS and thus, malware running on a virtual machine cannot harm the host OS. VMware Workstation¹² and Oracle VM VirtualBox¹³ are some of the virtual machine solutions available to analysts. In addition, there are several all-in-one software products based on sandboX technology that can be used to perform basic dynamic analysis. The most well-known is the Cuckoo Sandbox,¹⁴ an open source automated malware analysis system. This modular sandboX provides capabilities to trace API calls, analyze network traffic or perform memory analysis. Alternatively, there is a wide list of utilities for dynamically analyze malware and perform advanced and specific monitoring of some functionalities. Process Monitor is a tool for Windows that monitors certain registry, file system, network, process and thread activity. Process Explorer¹⁶ show the information about which handles and DLL processes are opened or loaded into the operating system. Regshot¹⁷ is a registry compare utility that allows snapshots of registries to be taken and compared. NetCat¹⁸ is a networking utility that can be used to monitor data transmission over a network. Wire- shark¹⁹ is an open

source sniffer that allows packets to be captured and network traffic to be intercepted and logged. Another indispensable software utility are debuggers. A debugger is used to examine the execution of another program. They provide a dynamic view of a program as it runs. The primary debugger of choice for malware analysts is OllyDbg²⁰, an x86 debugger that is free and has many plugins to extend its capabilities.

The risks of using virtualization and sandboXing for malware analysis is that some malware can detect when it is running in a virtual machine or a sandboX and subsequently, they will execute differently than when in a physical machine to make the job of malware analysts harder. In addition, even if you take all possible precautions, some risk is always present when analyzing malware. From time to time, vulnerabilities have been found in the virtualization tools that allow an attacker to exploit some of its features such as the shared folders feature.

2.4. MALWARE EVOLUTION

The diversity, sophistication, and availability of malicious software pose enormous challenges for securing networks and computer systems from attacks. Malware is constantly evolving and forces security analysts and researchers to keep pace by improving their cyber defenses. The proliferation of malware increased due to the use of polymorphic and metamorphic techniques used to evade detection and hide its true purpose. Polymorphic malware uses a polymorphic engine to mutate the code while keeping the original functionality intact. Packing and encryption are the two most common ways to hide code. Packers hide the real code of a program through one or more layers of compression. Then, at runtime the unpacking routines restore the original code in memory and execute it. Crypters encrypt and manipulate malware or part of its code, to make it harder for researchers to analyze the program. A crypter contains a stub used to encrypt and decrypt malicious code. Metamorphic malware rewrites its code to an equivalent whenever it is propagated. Malware authors may use multiple transformation techniques including, but not limited to, register renaming, code permutation, code expansion, code shrinking, and garbage code insertion. The combination of the aforementioned techniques resulted in rapidly growing malware volumes, making forensic investigations of malware cases time-consuming, costly, and more difficult.

Traditional antivirus solutions that relied on signature-based and heuristic/behavioral methods present some problems. A signature is a unique feature or set of features that uniquely distinguishes an executable, like a fingerprint. However, signature-based methods are unable to detect unknown malware variants. To tackle these challenges, security

analysts proposed behavior-based detection, which analyzes the file's characteristics and behavior to determine if it is indeed malware, though the scanning and analysis can take some time. To overcome the prior pitfalls of traditional antivirus engines and keep pace with new attacks and variants, researchers started adopting machine learning to complement their solutions, as machine learning is well suited for processing large volumes of data.

Fig. 2.4 Machine learning workflow.(Frederick et al 2020)

2.3.2 Malware Symptoms

According to the author (Samantray et al.,2018), it is concluded that the malware might be different in the method of propagation as well as infection but it could also be produced by similar symptoms. The Malware is infected through computers which might be an exhibit by the following methods

- The processing speed of the computer is slow
- Browser speed of the web is slow
- Network connection problem
- Usage of CPU is increased
- Icons, files, and storage program is advanced
- Crashing and freezing of the system
- Detection files or the automatic modification

- Messages /Emails being sent automatically without the user consents

The types of the malware along with the malware creators, concealment, symptoms, is determined (Samantray & Tripathy et al , 2018). Malware is described by various highlights and it differs depending on the kind of malware. The regular side effects or issues of a malware influenced PC remember ascend for a use of a CPU, decrease in a speed of a PC as well as relatively more slow PC, issues in building up an availability with a system, smashing or freezing of a framework, cancellation or robbery of an information as well as surprising adjustments of a document, arbitrary event of the strange records, programs and so on., running and reconfiguring of the projects without anyone else, unapproved killing of the antivirus in the framework, sending and getting messages without information

2.4.1 Malware Detection Techniques

Researchers develop malware detection systems and keep track of malicious programs and benign software towards analyzing those applications in order. Malware detection techniques can be classified into three categories including

- signature-based,
- anomaly-based, and
- heuristic-based.

In this section, we discuss malware detection systems and present the result and possible limitations.

2.5 APPROACH TO DETECTING MALWARE

Over the past decade there has been an increase in the research and deployment of machine learning solutions to tackle the tasks of malware detection and classification. The success and consolidation of machine learning approaches would not have been possible without the confluence of three recent developments:

- The first development is the increase in labeled feeds of malware meaning that, for the first time, labeled malware is available not only to the security community but also to the research community. The size of these feeds ranges from limited high-quality samples, like the ones provided by Microsoft (Ronen et al., 2018) for the Big Data Innovators Gathering Anti-Malware Prediction Challenge, to huge volumes of malware, such as the Zoo (Yuval Nativ, 2015) or Virus Share (2011).
- The second development is that computational power has increased rapidly and at the same time has become cheaper and closer to the budget of most researchers.

Consequently, it allowed researchers to speed-up in the iterative training process and to fit larger and more complex models to the ever-increasing data.

- Third, the machine learning field has evolved at an increased pace during the last decades, achieving breakthrough success in terms of accuracy and scalability on a wide range of tasks, such as computer vision, speech recognition and natural language processing.

In machine learning, a workflow is an iterative process that involves gathering available data, cleaning and preparing the data, building models, validating and deploying into production. See Fig. 2. Instead of dealing with raw malware, the data preparation process of traditional machine learning approaches involves preprocessing the executable to extract a set of features that provide an abstract view of the software. Afterwards the features are used to train a model to solve the task at hand. Because of the variety of malware functionalities, it is important not only to detect malicious software, but also to differentiate between different kinds of malware in order to provide a better understanding of their capabilities. The main difference between machine learning solutions for detection or classification of malware is the output returned by the system implemented. On the one hand, a malware detection system outputs a single value $y = f(x)$, in the range from 0 to 1, which indicates the maliciousness of the executable. On the other hand, a classification system outputs the probability of a given executable belonging to each output class or family, $y \in \mathbb{R}^N$, where N indicates the number of different families.

2.6 CHALLENGES IN MALWARE DETECTION

According to the author Kuntz et al (2017), whenever a system is infected by malware the IT staff tries to re-image the computer to better understand the malware and the ways that can be used for its prevention. Although cost-effective this may not be the best possible solution. Some malicious software directly attaches to system BIOS and can remain on the device even if it is re-imaged. A software company by the name of the “Hacking Team” developed a tool which attaches itself to a computer’s UEFI and it reinstalls itself even if the hard is wiped clean. Due to this, malware can be present even though the end-user or IT staff is unaware of it. Some types of viruses can change the firmware when being installed hence not being able to be detected by any anti-virus software. This methodology may be cost-effective in the short term does not work well in the long term as it can impose fines on organizations for not being HIPAA compliant. In case of malware detection and prevention in an organization, proper documentation is necessary so that this does not happen to anyone else again and if this happens, they know what measures to take. One of

the ways to overcome malware is that software companies should provide bounties for finding out software flaws. The flaw is that software development takes more time than finding bugs (Kuntz et al , 2017).

COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF RESEARCH PAPERS

Comparison of my work(2022) and Previous work

S.No	Year	Title	Algorithms used	work
1.	2022	Malware Detection Using Machine Learning	CNN, RNN, Decision Tree, Random Forest	Focusing on the usage of RNN and CNN Algorithms for Malware detection and comparing with other algorithms such as Decision Tree and Random Forest. Focusing on detecting malwares in different formats like not only PE files.
2.	2021	Applying Convolutional Neural Network for Malware Detection	CNN	Only focuses on the use of CNN algorithm for malware detection.
3.	2019	Detection of advanced malware by Machine Learning techniques	Decision Tree, Random Forest, Naive Bayes, J48 Graft	Use of signature-based method which is traditional and does not provide best accuracy.

4.	2017	Malware Detection using Machine Learning Based Analysis of Virtual Memory Access Patterns	SVM, Random forest	Human input is a necessity which limits automation, Size of histogram is to be chosen carefully.
5.	2020	Classification Of Malware Detection using Machine Learning Algorithms	Naive bayes, support vector machine, random forest, K- nearest Neighbor	Only focuses on the use of machine learning algorithms for malware detection.
6.	2009	N-Grams based file signatures for malware detection	KNN algorithm	Good detection ratio is only achieved for higher values of N.
15	2008	Learning and Classification of Malware Behavior	Support Vector Machine	Relies on single program execution of a malware binary.

8	2006	Learning to Detect and Classify Malicious Executable in the Wild	Naive bayes, Support vector machine	The relative performance of methods used in this paper was not as good as the previous one.
9	2008	Metamorphic Virus: Analysis and Detection	Random decryption algorithm (RDA)	Some viruses cannot be detected even in an emulated environment
10	2006	Machine Learning for Computer Security	Adaptive statistical compression algorithms	The adversary can defeat the computer that learns how to extract signatures for detecting computer worms.
11	2019	Malware Detection using Machine Learning and Deep Learning	Randomforest and KNN Algorithm	Does not apply any recurrent neural networks for malware detection.
12	2017	Malware using Machine Learning Algorithms	SVM, Decision Tree, Naive Bayes and Multi-Naive Bayes Algorithm	Use of signature-based method which is traditional.
13	2017	Malware Detection and Evasion with Machine Learning Techniques: A Survey	Heuristic, Artificial Intelligence, Behavior, Signature Based Methods	Use of traditional methods for malware detection.
14	2012	Malware Detection Module using Machine Learning Algorithms to Assist in Centralized Security in Enterprise Networks	Decision Tree, Random Forest, Naive Bayes	Some methods of machine learning are not appropriate due to heavy processors.

Table1: COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF RESEARCH PAPERS

2.7 RELATED WORK

Tal Garfinkel and Mendel Rosenblum [48] proposed a virtual machine monitoring approach to detect malicious software. An architectural framework (Fig. 11) was introduced that maintains the transparency of the host-based Intrusion detection system (IDS) but for larger attack resistance they kept the IDS away from the host. The evaluation indicates to achieve distinct ability to moderate interactions between host and principal software by using virtual machine monitor. However, the risk of errors and tamper resistance is the limitation of the proposed approach.

(Shanxi Li et al., 2021) proposes a malware classifier based on graph convolutional network, designed to adapt to the difference of malware characteristics. The approach first extracts the API call sequence from the malware code and generates a directed cycle graph followed by extracting the feature map of the graph, and designing a classifier based on graph convolutional network using the Markov chain and principal component analysis method. The method also analyzes and compares the performance of the method. An evaluation result indicates the highest accuracy is 98.32. % which is superior compared to other existing methods in terms of FPR and accuracy Other than that, (Long Wen et al., 2017)] propose a machine learning-based lightweight system with the goal of identifying unknown malware on Android devices. The proposed approach extract features based on static analysis and dynamic analysis. The researchers also introduce a new feature selection algorithm PCA-RELIEF towards disposing of the raw features. The demonstration achieved better performance with a higher detection rate and lower error detection.

CHAPTER THREE

SYSTEM ANALYSIS AND DESIGN

3.1 SYSTEM DESIGN

The main deliverable for this directed project is a systems design detailing a proposed system for improving, automating, and solving existing problems within the current malware analysis system. A formal systems development methodology will be followed, consisting primarily of a document detailing the architecture, systems context, and technical requirements of the proposed system. Personal study of several journals have formed the basis for understanding the “state of the art” of systems development strategies. Use cases will provide evidence of the various interactions that users need to have with the system, and will shape the desired state of the system after completion. **It is important to note that actual software will NOT be part of the deliverable for this directed project.**

In systems design, and particularly software design, a common methodology for the development of a new system is the Systems Development Life Cycle, or SDLC (Satzinger, et al, 2002). The SDLC contains the following phases of systems development:

- Planning – determine the purpose of the system.
- Analysis – determine what the system needs to do, the goals for the system and how to determine if those goals have been met.
- Design – determine how the system will work, what the overall architecture is, and determine what steps would need to be taken to construct an actual system.
- Implementation – using the existing design, construct a system to meet the requirements of the project.
- Testing – establish that the constructed system actually does meet the requirements detailed in the design.
- Maintenance – fix bugs in the system, which are essentially differences between the design (requirements) and the constructed system (reality). As the design inevitably changes, update the actual system to match these changes.

As mentioned, this project is not a software construction project, but instead is a software design project. The SDLC will be followed through the first three steps. This document constitutes the “planning” phase of the SDLC, as it is discussing the purpose of the system.

It begins to address the “analysis” phase, as it has discussed gaps between the current system and the desired system (problems and limitations), which will be used to determine if the proposed system has met its goals. The primary deliverable of the directed project will consist of the remainder of the “analysis” phase and the entire “design” phase. The goal is to provide a technically complete design which would be sufficient to guide someone through software construction, without being so specific as to lock a developer into a technology or set of technologies. Essentially, the directed project will provide a roadmap for development of the automated malware detection and analysis system. The final step of the project will be to validate the design against the current-state challenges identified in Table 2 and Table 4.

Time Action Plan

This table illustrates the phases in the incident Response Plan.

3.2 Systems Context Diagram

The schematic diagram of SVM-based malware detection (Wenjia et al., 2015)

Detection and Analysis Process Flow Diagram

System Administrators – allowed to add and remove users from the system in order to manage and control access to use it.

Malware Researchers – primary actors in the context of the system, will configure cases for analysis and retrieve final analysis reports when completed.

Customers – drivers and motivation for the system, will provide images to researchers and retrieve final reports when completed.

File Store – external resource (pre-existing to the system) that provides the actual disk images to be used for the analysis process.

3.3 Use Case Diagram

Use Case Name:	Add New Image
Priority:	High
Primary Business Actor:	Researcher
Primary System Actor:	
Description:	This use case describes the process of a malware researcher entering and loading a new disk image for analysis with the system.
Pre-condition :	Target disk image has been copied to file store.
Typical Course of Events:	1) →Researcher authenticates to analysis system.
	2) ←System validates researcher’s credentials.
	3) →Researcher adds new case file to system.
	4) ←System prompts for case description and location of target disk image.
	5) →Researcher provides case background, supporting information, and location of disk image.
	6) ←System queues pending analysis job.
	7) ←System notifies researcher when analysis is complete.
Alternate Courses:	2) ←System rejects researcher’s credentials, access is denied.

Use Case Name:	Remove User
Priority:	Medium
Primary Business Actor:	Administrator
Primary System Actor:	
Description:	This use case describes the process of the system administrator removing a user account from the system.
Pre-condition:	User no longer needs access to the system.
Typical Course of Events:	1) →Administrator authenticates to analysis system.
	2) ←System validates administrator's credentials.
	3) →Administrator issues command to remove user.
	4) ←System verifies that administrator wants to remove account.
	5) →Administrator confirms or denies deletion.
	6) ←System removes account.
Alternate Courses:	2) ←System rejects administrator's credentials, access is denied.
	6) →System does not remove account.
Conclusion:	This use case concludes when the account has been removed.
Post-condition:	

Sequence illustration for malware detection system(Hyo sik, 2014)

3.4 System Architecture Diagram

Architecture of the malware Detection System (Shijonn et al., 2013)

The items depicted above represent logical components of the system; their physical allocation is intentionally not described. Due to the desired scalability of the system, it is presumed that these components can and will exist anywhere.

3.5 WORKFLOW

- A disk image for a new case to be analyzed is copied to the File Store.
- Using the web-based Management Interface, information about the case (including the location of the image) is entered into the Database.
- The Analysis Coordinator serves as the master node for the operation of the analysis system. Upon seeing a new case, it determines which sub-tasks need to be completed.
- Tasks are distributed to the Worker Nodes for processing.
- The Worker Nodes access resources from the File Store as necessary, copying resources like disk images locally for processing.
- Upon completing their respective tasks, the Worker Nodes notify the Analysis Coordinator.

- The Analysis Coordinator performs final cleanup tasks and updates the Database with the results.

3.6 SYSTEM ANALYSIS FUNCTIONAL REQUIREMENTS

- The system shall use a relational database to store input metadata, in-progress operational data, and completed results.
- The system shall provide a secured user interface for entering new cases into the system, as well as for generating reports about completed cases.
- An administrative interface shall be provided for management of users within the system.
- Analysis of cases should be coordinated by a single machine/entity, which is responsible for dividing workload among one or more “worker” machines.
- Independent tasks within the detection and analysis phases shall be executed concurrently, saving wall clock time and yielding a quicker turnaround time on case results.
- Analysis shall consist of two phases, to be completed sequentially: detection of malware, and behavioral analysis of malware.
- The detection phase should at minimum consist of the following steps. These steps will be completed once for each malware detection tool that is used, and will be able to execute concurrently on multiple worker machines:
 - Copy active case’s disk image from file store to local disk.
 - Locate existing virtual machine on local disk for selected malware detection tool (preconfigured).
 - Reconfigure virtual machine to use copied local disk image.
 - Boot up virtual machine.
 - Execute script within Windows virtual machine that will use automation to begin scanning disk image using chosen malware detection tool.
 - Following completion of malware detection, script should capture results and report them back to the analysis coordinator. If detection phase is completed, remove disk image from local drive.
- The analysis coordinator shall distribute detection phase work among worker machines until all chosen malware detection tools have been used.
- The analysis coordinator shall convert all results into a unified format and store those results in the database.

- Using the stored results, the system shall identify individual pieces of suspected malware from the active case.
- The analysis coordinator shall assign a task to a worker machine which will open the disk image, and extract all pieces of suspected malware to a temporary location.
- The worker machine shall submit all of the suspected malware to the private analysis service (using an intermediate submission frontend).
- The submission frontend shall process each piece of malware with the private analysis service, and upon receiving results they should be stored in the database with the other case information.
- After all pieces of suspected malware have been behaviorally analyzed, the analysis coordinator shall create a final report of all malware found within the disk image and mark the case as “completed.”
- The system shall notify the user who submitted the case that processing is complete.
- The user shall be able to use the management interface to retrieve the final report of located malware.

CHAPTER FOUR SYSTEM IMPLEMENTATION

4.0 INTRODUCTION

Implementing different types of classifiers to develop malware detection and prevention systems shall provide better and using AI shall bring a significant advantage to detect and prevent unknown malicious activities. We display a flowchart of unknown malware detection using artificial intelligence. In this Chapter, we provide a detailed review on each method of Malware Detection.

- The signature-based detection method consists of four components as depicted in Fig. 6 is a term that helps in identifying and detecting attacks by looking for specific patterns (Onyedeké et al., 2020). In a signature-based method, developers use a database containing signatures of viruses, scan the file, and evaluate information with that database for detecting malware in the database. If the information matches with the database's data that means the file contains viruses. The primary advantage of this method is effective for the known malware, however, it has limitations in detecting unknown malware (Ye li et al., 2019). Fig. 4.1 shows Intrusion Detection System (IDS) keeps a statistical model of traffic that also can be referred to a database, IDS accepts traffic from various sources and matches it with statistical traffic to find out whether it is malicious or not and then provides the result to an administrator

4.1 SYSTEM DESIGN FLOWCHART

Fig 4.1 Flow chart of AI Based Unknown Malware Detection Techniques(Yeli 2009)

fig 4.2

Anomaly-based Detection Technique: Anomaly-based network intrusion detection plays a vital role in addressing security issues and protecting networks against malicious activities. Anomaly-based methods address the limitations of signature-based techniques by enabling to detect any of known or unknown malware by applying classification techniques over activities of a system for malware detection. Such transformation from pattern-based detection to a classification-based approach to identify normal or anomalous behavior gives an advantage of detecting malware activities

Fig 4.3 Common anomaly-based network IDS (Prasad et al., 2019)

Fig. 4.4 Anomaly Based IDS (Saad et al., 2019)

Fig. 8 depicts the anomaly-based Network Intrusion Detection System (IDS) where the functional stages are normally adopted in the anomaly-based network intrusion detection systems (ANIDS). On the other hand, Fig. 9 illustrates a connection with a database consists of the signature of known attacks, with the common signatures coming from different packets with that database, an alert is sent to the system admin if the unknown signature matches with known signature mean malware detected.

Heuristic-based Detection Technique: Applying Artificial Intelligence over the signature and anomaly-based detection systems improve the efficiency of malware detection. However, in order to adopt environmental change and improve prediction ability, a machine learning algorithm named genetic algorithm along with neural network was applied over malware detection system to improve the classification method. The algorithm applies characteristics such as inheritance, selection, and combination that give the advantage to attain optimum solutions from multiple directions without any previous knowledge about the system (Vaughn et al 2002). The combination of statistical and mathematical techniques improves the heuristic method from previous methods. Fig. 9 represents the features of Heuristic Methods.

4.2 CHOICE OF PROGRAMMING LANGUAGE

For several years now, Python has been a dominant language in cybersecurity. It is a server-side scripting language, so the resulting script doesn't need compiling by coders. It's a general-purpose language that is used in many — if not most — cybersecurity situation. With Python, you're able to automate tasks and perform malware analysis. Plus an extensive third-party library of scripts is readily accessible, meaning help is right around the corner. Code readability, clear and easy syntax, and a vast number of libraries are some of the aspects that make it popular. For cybersecurity experts, Python is a valuable programming language since it can be used in detecting malware, penetration testing, scanning, and analyzing cyber threats. If you understand Python, being a SOC support pro makes a whole lot of sense.

4.3 ENVIRONMENT

Malware Detection application would work perfectly on any computer running windows 7,8,10, linux OS, Ubuntu and also the IOS platform. It was written in a python compiler with multi-platform capabilities. It is flexible for more functions and features that would be implemented in the future when the need arises. Nevertheless, in order to successfully create this system and bring to reality this research work.

4.4 SYSTEM REQUIREMENT

Software Requirements

- Ubuntu 18.04
- Virtual Box 6.0

Hardware Requirements

- RAM 2GB
- CPU
- Uninterruptable Power Supply
- Intel Core i5- 8265u

4.6 SYSTEM IMPLEMENTATION

The application was developed on a windows 10 machine, 64bits operating system. It was implemented using Open-cv Python as the back-end programming language. Source finder was used to identify the source Code.

CHAPTER FIVE

SUMMARY AND CONCLUSION

6.1. CONCLUSION

Our main target was to come up with a machine learning framework that generically detects as much malware samples as it can, with the tough constraint of having a zero false positive rate. We were very close to our goal, although we still have a non-zero false positive rate. In order that this framework to become part of a highly competitive commercial product, a number of deterministic exception mechanisms have to be added. In our opinion, malware detection via machine learning will not replace the standard detection methods used by anti-virus vendors, but will come as an addition to them. Any commercial anti-virus product is subject to certain speed and memory limitations, therefore the most reliable algorithms

Summing up all the discussion from above, it is concluded that malware attacks can create a lot of problems and issue to the whole personal computer. Therefore, it is important to detect malware and also remove it from the system. Due to this, the whole system will be protected from it. The main aim of this research is to use machine learning technique to detect malware samples present in the system. If malware detection is used properly with the tough constraint, then false positive rate must be zero. The results are showing that the required goals are not achieved and it is extremely close to the main goal but there is still non-zero false positive rate. Due to this framework, the particular part of the system is considered a highly competitive commercial product with different number of deterministic expectation mechanism. Therefore, it is become simple to detect malware from the files by using machine learning approaches. Another point is that decision tree and Random Forest algorithms are the best one because they can easily detect malware from the large dataset. If these algorithms are improved, then it is possible to obtain required results about malware detection. Compare to these four Algorithms CNN, RNN, Decision Tree and Random Forest. I got more accuracy in CNN. So, CNN is the best algorithm among these four for malware detection.

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